

FutureTDM

Explore . Analyse . Improve

REDUCING BARRIERS AND INCREASING UPTAKE OF TEXT AND DATA MINING FOR RESEARCH ENVIRONMENTS USING A COLLABORATIVE KNOWLEDGE AND OPEN INFORMATION APPROACH

Deliverable D4.4

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Website: <http://www.futuretdm.eu/>

E-Mail: office@futuretdm.eu

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Authors:	Maria Eskevich, RU Antal van den Bosch, RU
Contributors:	Stelios Piperidis, ARC Kanella Pouli, ARC Maria Gavriilidou, ARC Dimitris Galanis, ARC
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1 SUMMARY

This report provides information about the work on the scientific review paper that gives a critical review of the past, present and future of the state-of-the-art of the field of text and data mining (TDM). This publication aims to broaden perspective on the past, current, and future trends in TDM amongst audience, outlined via desktop research, consultation with the practitioners (Deliverables D.4.3. and D4.5.) and scientific communities. Report includes brief description of publication venue selection, text of the paper that can be further updated with the open accesses reviewers comments.

Additionally, the information about the update of FutureTDM knowledge base collection of relevant projects, organisations, methods and tools is provided including the current list of the collections in the Annex.

2 WORK ON THE SCIENTIFIC PAPER

2.1 Criteria for selection of potential publication venues

We have defined the two main criteria for the target publication venues:

- Diverse type of TDM applications already present in the journal
- The journal has to be Open Access, or at least to have the open access publication option

As the review of TDM work from the perspective of overall scientific development and insights on its visibility across different economic fields, that are formulated within the FutureTDM consortium, differ from the traditional type of publication content that is expected by journals, we took an initiative to contact a number of targeted journals in order to find a venue that would fit our criteria and to ensure that our content would be suitable. These were the journals to contact:

1. Data Science Journal

- Link: <http://datascience.codata.org>
- Aims and scope of the journal: The CODATA Data Science Journal is a peer-reviewed, open access, electronic journal, publishing papers on the management, dissemination, use and reuse of research data and databases across all research domains, including science, technology, the humanities and the arts. The scope of the journal includes descriptions of data systems, their implementations and their publication, applications, infrastructures, software, legal, reproducibility and transparency issues, the availability and usability of complex datasets, and with a particular focus on the principles, policies and practices for open data. All data is in scope, whether born digital or converted from other sources.
 - *Reviews* can cover topics such as current controversies, the current “state of the art” or the historical development of studies as well as issues of regional or temporal focus. Papers should critically engage with the relevant body of extant literature. Review articles should be no longer than 3,000 words in length.
- Open access policy: multidisciplinary Open Access journal

2. PLOSOne

- Link: <http://journals.plos.org/plosone/>
- Aims and scope of the journal: PLOS ONE features reports of original research from all disciplines within science and medicine. By not excluding research on the basis of subject area, PLOS ONE facilitates the discovery of connections between research whether within or between disciplines.

- We consider publishing systematic reviews only if the methods ensure the comprehensive and unbiased sampling of existing literature.
- Submissions describing methods, software, databases, or other tools. We consider submissions describing methods, software, databases, or other tools if they follow the appropriate reporting guidelines.
- Qualitative research. We consider publishing qualitative research only if it adheres to appropriate study design and reporting guidelines.
- Studies reporting negative results.
- Open access policy: multidisciplinary Open Access journal

3. DSH (Digital Scholarship for Humanities)

- Link: <https://academic.oup.com/dsh>
- Aims and scope of the journal: *DSH or Digital Scholarship in the Humanities* is an international, peer reviewed journal which publishes original contributions on all aspects of digital scholarship in the Humanities including, but not limited to, the field of what is currently called the Digital Humanities. Long and short papers report on theoretical, methodological, experimental, and applied research and include results of research projects, descriptions and evaluations of tools, techniques, and methodologies, and reports on work in progress. *DSH* also publishes reviews of books and resources.
- Open access policy: multidisciplinary Open Access journal

4. Science Communication (SAGE)

- Web-Link: <http://journals.sagepub.com/home/scx>
- Aims and scope of the journal: Science Communication is an international, interdisciplinary social science journal that examines such topics as the nature of scientific expertise as represented through communication and the processes or effects characterizing the communication of science in any context. Science is broadly defined to include environmental science, health science, and technology. Science Communication welcomes submissions of empirical research from authors in all relevant disciplines (including the social sciences, the humanities, and science itself). Both qualitative and quantitative research papers with a basis in theory are acceptable. Preference is given to articles that bridge the gap between theory and practice and that will be of interest across disciplines. In addition to peer-reviewed research, Science Communication publishes commentaries that analyse issues and trends in the field – whether scholarly, professional, or policy-related – and a periodic summary of new books in the field.
- Open access policy: OA option is available

5. IEEE Access

- Web-Link: <http://ieeaccess.ieee.org/learn-more-about-ieee-access/>

- Aims and scope of the journal: IEEE Access publishes articles that are of high interest to readers: original, technically correct, and clearly presented. The scope of this journal comprises all of IEEE's fields of interest, emphasizing applications-oriented and interdisciplinary articles. IEEE Access also accepts traditional technical articles, as well as reviews and surveys.
- Open access policy: Multidisciplinary Open Access Journal, fee \$1,750 per article

Eventually, we have chosen the “Data Science Journal” that is an open access multidisciplinary journal run by an SME publisher “Ubiquity Press”.

2.2 Information on the submitted paper

The details of the submission are the following:

- Authors: Maria Eskevich, Stelios Piperidis, Kanella Pouli, Maria Gavriilidou, Dimitris Galanis, Antal van den Bosch.
- Title: Text and Data Mining: Past, present, and future.
- Submission date: 01.05.2017.
- Text of the paper is in the Appendix

3 WORK ON THE FUTURETDM KNOWLEDGE BASE ENRICHMENT

3.1 Collection of Projects

FutureTDM collection of projects by the Deliverable submission date contains 140 items, 37 of which are already integrated into the platform. For 7 of the projects it is not possible to assign an economic sector, such as (+)Spaces , while the other 133 can be assigned to one or even a combination of sectors due to the multidisciplinary nature of the projects. Table 1 contains the overall statistics of the number of projects in the collection.

Sector or combination of Sectors that that the project is assigned to	Number of projects
Primary-Sector, Secondary-Sector, Tertiary-Sector, Quaternary-Sector	1
Primary-Sector, Quaternary-Sector	1
Secondary-Sector	8
Secondary-Sector, Tertiary-Sector	3
Secondary-Sector, Quaternary-Sector	38
Secondary-Sector, Tertiary-Sector, Quaternary-Sector	6
Tertiary-Sector	13
Tertiary-Sector, Quaternary-Sector	24
Quaternary-Sector	38
Quinary-Sector	1
TOTAL	133

Table 1: Total number of projects in the FutureTDM Knowledge Base Collection structured by economic sector

3.2 Collection of Organisations

FutureTDM collection of organisations by the Deliverable submission date contains 72 items, 59 of which are already integrated into the platform. 55 of these organisations have only one EU-country location, while three of them spread across more than one country within the EU, and 6 have locations outside EU in USA.

Company locations details	Country	Number
Company is based in one country	Austria	1
	Belgium	2
	Czech Republic	2
	Denmark	2
	Finland	1
	France	4
	Germany	10
	Greece	3
	Ireland	1
	Italy	3
	Norway	1
	Slovenia	1
	Spain	4
	Sweden	2
	Switzerland	4
The Netherlands	5	
UK	9	
Company has offices internationally	Belgium, The Netherlands, Germany, USA	1
	The Netherlands,	1
	Germany/USA	1
	Ireland/Greece	1
	Spain/UK	1
	UK/USA	2
	USA, many	2
Companies outside EU	Japan	1
	USA	7
TOTAL		72

Table 2: Total number of projects in the FutureTDM Knowledge Base Collection structured by country

3.3 Collection of Methods

FutureTDM collection of projects splits scientific methods into 29 items, and all of them are integrated into the platform, as they are used to specify the organisations focus.

TDM Methods			
Artificial Intelligence	Machine Learning	Statistics	Kernel Methods
Association rules	Machine Translation	Summarisation	Ensemble Learning
Classification	Multimedia Processing	Term/Concept Extraction	Dimensionality Reduction
Clustering	Natural Language Processing	Text Mining	Decision Trees
Data Mining	Negation and Modality Detection	Textual Entailment	Deep Learning
Graph Mining	Predictive Analytics	Artificial Neural Networks	
Information Extraction	Regression	Bayesian Inference	
Information Retrieval	Sentiment Analysis/Opinion Mining	Instance-Based Learning	

Table 3: FutureTDM text and data mining methods collection

3.4 Collection of Tools

FutureTDM collection of projects by the Deliverable submission date contains 72 items, 59 of which are already integrated into the platform. Table contains the complete list of tools collected so far.

Name	URL
ALVEO	http://alveo.edu.au/
Alvis	https://migale.jouy.inra.fr/redmine/projects/alvisnlp
Angoss Knowledge STUDIO	http://www.angoss.com/
AnnoMarket	https://annomarket.eu/
Apache cTAKES	http://ctakes.apache.org
Apache OpenNLP	http://opennlp.apache.org
Apache UIMA	https://uima.apache.org
Argo	http://argo.nactem.ac.uk

BioCatalogue	https://www.biocatalogue.org/
BiodiversityCatalogue	https://www.biodiversitycatalogue.org
Bluima	https://github.com/BlueBrain/bluima
CLARIN-DK	http://clarin.dk/
ClearTK	https://cleartk.github.io/cleartk
Clementine	http://datamining.togaware.com/survivor/Clementine.html
ContentMine	http://www.contentmine.org/
DKPro Core	https://dkpro.github.io/dkpro-core
ELKI	http://elki.dbs.ifi.lmu.de/
FICO Data Management	http://www.fico.com/
Galaxy	https://galaxyproject.org/
GATE Embedded	https://gate.ac.uk
Heart of Gold	http://heartofgold.dfki.de
IBM SPSS Predictive Analysis	http://www-03.ibm.com/software/products/en/spss-predictive-analytics-enterprise
JCoRe	http://julielab.github.io
Jpylyzer	http://jpylyzer.openpreservation.org/
KAF	http://kyoto-project.eu/xmlgroup.iit.cnr.it/kyoto/index2091.html?option=com_content&view=article&id=504&Itemid=173
Kepler	https://kepler-project.org/
KNIME	http://www.knime.org/knime
Language Grid	http://langrid.org/en/index.html
LAPPS Grid	http://www.lappsgrid.org/
Massive Online Analysis (MOA)	http://moa.cms.waikato.ac.nz/
Matchbox	http://matchbox.openpreservation.org/
Microsoft SQL Server	https://technet.microsoft.com/en-

Analysis Service (SSAS)	us/library/ms175609%28v=sql.90%29.aspx
Neural Designer	https://www.neuraldesigner.com/
NLTK	http://www.nltk.org
Open Calais	www.opencalais.com/
Oracle Data Miner GUI	http://www.oracle.com/technetwork/database/options/odm/dataminerworkflow-168677.html
Orange	http://orange.biolab.si/
Pagelyzer	http://pagelyzer.openpreservation.org/
Pegasus	https://pegasus.isi.edu
Pentaho	http://www.pentaho.com/
Pipeline Pilot	http://accelrys.com/products/collaborative-science/biovia-pipeline-pilot/
QT21	http://qt21.metashare.ilsp.gr/
Rapidminer Radoop	www.rapidminer.com
Rapidminer Server	www.rapidminer.com
Rapidminer Studio	www.rapidminer.com
SAP Hana	https://hana.sap.com
SAS Data Mining	http://www.sas.com
SPSS	http://www.ibm.com/analytics/us/en/technology/spss/
Taverna	http://www.taverna.org.uk/
Think Analytics	http://thinkanalytics.com/
Think Enterprise Data Miner	www.thinkanalytics.com/
Triana	http://www.trianacode.org
TTNWW	http://yago.meertens.knaw.nl/apache/TTNWW/
Weblicht	https://weblicht.sfs.uni-tuebingen.de/
WEKA	http://www.cs.waikato.ac.nz/~ml/weka
xcorrSound	http://xcorrSound.openpreservation.org/

VisTrails	http://www.vistrails.org
Trendminer	https://www.trendminer.com/
Opendatasoft	https://www.opendatasoft.com/
Meta	http://meta.com/
TensorFlow	https://www.tensorflow.org/about/
Epinium	http://epinium.com/
Exclusivi	http://exclusivi.com/hotels/
Eparkomat	http://www.eparkomat.com/
Data Scouts	https://datascouts.eu/
TopPlace	http://www.avuxi.com/products/topplace
Influency	https://influency.com/en/
Plazi TreatmentBank	http://plazi.org/api-tools/api/#Plazi_API
SafeToNet	https://safetonet.com/
Egas	https://demo.bmd-software.com/egas/
Wordfreak	http://wordfreak.sourceforge.net/
Theano	https://github.com/Theano/

Table 4: Total list of tools in the FutureTDM Knowledge Base Collection

4 CONCLUSIONS

This Deliverable contains the full text of submitted TDM review paper, together with the explanation on the publication venue selection.

We provide quantitative updates on the progress with filling in the four main categories of the Knowledge Base Collection, while the Deliverables 6.1, 6.2 and 6.3¹ contains the qualitative description of the technology behind the FutureTDM Platform.

¹ www.futuretdm.eu

5 ANNEX

In the following we present the scientific paper “**Text and Data Mining: Past, present, and future**” and the collections below described in the previous section. The list will be given in this order:

- Collection of Organisations
- Collection of Projects
- Collection of Tools

Text and Data Mining: Past, present, and future

Maria Eskevich¹, Stelios Piperidis², Kanella Pouli²,
Maria Gavriilidou², Dimitris Galanis², Antal van den Bosch¹

¹*Radboud University, Nijmegen, Netherlands,*

²*Institute for Language and Speech Processing (ILSP), "Athena" R.C., Greece*

Abstract

In this paper we review text and data mining (TDM) as a set of data science techniques that detect information from massive amounts of data, present this information for further analysis, and support data-driven decision making. We summarise state-of-the-art TDM trends from a scientific perspective, and outline their application in industrial setting. We analyse the spread of TDM across diverse economic sectors via such parameters as publication and funding volumes in the context of research within the European Union as an example.

Keywords: Text and Data Mining, Data Science, Big Data, Review, Trends

1. Introduction

Text and Data Mining has been defined as “the discovery by computer of new, previously unknown information, by automatically extracting and relating information from different (...) resources, to reveal otherwise hidden meanings” [17], in other words, “an exploratory data analysis that leads to the discovery of heretofore unknown information, or to answers for questions for which the answer is not currently known” [17]. Nowadays, this umbrella term encompasses diverse techniques that allow for the interpretation of content of any type ranging from raw data, e.g. sensor data, text, images and multimedia, to processed content and structured data, e.g. diagrams, charts, references, maps, formulas, chemical structures, and metadata, on a large scale through the identification of patterns.

Components of TDM existed before the formal introduction of the term within the scientific community. Essentially TDM has grown as part of the general ‘data science’ field from a number of parent scientific disciplines, notably artificial intelligence and its subdisciplines such as machine learning, pattern recognition, and natural language processing, as well as mathematics, statistics, and information retrieval. It has benefited from multidisciplinary approaches and collaborations across these fields.

The growing quantity of digital content currently produced by society, as well as efforts on the digitization of archives, in combination with the potential ease of access to this data at any location via easy-to-use devices (with reliable Internet connection, and mobile devices) increase both the need for content mining technologies, and their proliferation in the fabric of modern society [29].

TDM is becoming increasingly ubiquitous on the global market, as each company that tracks its activities, products, and communications in some digital form has the potential to reuse this data for further analysis and improvement. For some sectors, countries and applications, it is already possible to estimate the potential profit or at least the size of the market [29, 9]. Other fields such as journalism, which is in the process of embracing the concept of Data Journalism, have to first agree on the conceptual changes required to their current work behaviour in order to merge the traditional work pattern with TDM [20].

This paper is structured as follows. We first survey the scientific trends and outline the most prominent scientific communities that develop the state-of-the-art algorithms and aim to advance beyond those (Section 2). Section 3 provides examples of the TDM scientific work in application across economic structure using the European Union as a case example. Section 4 then discusses future trends and their overall potential.

2. Scientific perspective: Research fields supporting TDM

Text and data mining has gradually evolved into a large multidisciplinary field with complex approaches for a range of applications that can be found in all types of human activities. Historically, the development of mining technologies has its roots with the invention of mathematical models [14] and statistical analysis [8]. Due to the advent of computers and systems for storing larger quantities of data, the possibility to mine large datasets and filter relevant information has greatly expanded what used to be laborious

expert analysis work. Since the beginning of the 1990s, modern data mining tools have appeared on the market and in labs, allowing more advanced analysis, to discover hidden patterns and to extract implicit knowledge in any domain, as envisaged and pioneered for the life science domain by Swanson in [41].

With the invention and adoption of the World Wide Web [4], researchers expanded their efforts to develop text and data mining methods to search and explore the web. This led to the creation of search engines, starting from simple interface-based browsers such as *Mosaic* and *Netscape*, and developed into large-scale systems such as *Google* and *Bing*. This, together with the advances in natural language processing, formed the opening gambit towards more complex approaches of text mining to different fields (such as the biomedical domain, economics, social sciences, or humanities), and types of data and content (such as scientific publications and research data, social media, multimedia, or public sector information).

The core research fields that develop, test, and publish the algorithms for TDM implementations for each specific domain of use, are

- *machine learning (ML)*, which is the automated learning of tasks and the discovery of patterns and structure in data [1];
- *information retrieval (IR) and search*, which focuses on the optimisation of search methods that, based on an index of vast amounts of content, allow for the location and extraction of the most relevant facts answering any question and user type [37]; and
- *natural language processing (NLP)* techniques, which deal with human language in its textual and spoken form [21, 27].

Research progress within TDM-related communities can be traced across two main sources: a number of high-impact yearly conferences (such as Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining (KDD), International Conference on Data Engineering (ICDE), IEEE International Conference on Data Mining (ICDM) for ML; ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval (SIGIR) and International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management (CIKM) for IR; Annual meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL) and Conference on Empirical Methods on Natural Language Processing (EMNLP) for NLP), and a set of prominent journals in the fields (such as IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering (TKDE), Information Processing Letters (IPL)

for ML; Information Retrieval Journal for IR; Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics (TACL) for NLP). With the speed of technology development and the race for implementation of new methods in the context of practical implementations, the publications at conferences, having the fastest turnaround, have a relatively high impact. There is also a noteworthy trend to pre-print publications via open access self-archiving services such as <https://arxiv.org/>, that originally was created for the field of physics, but gradually expanded to include mathematics, computer science, nonlinear sciences, quantitative biology, quantitative finance, and statistics. This pre-print culture has an impact on the publications acceptance at the traditional publication venues that needs to take into account these additional aspects when the reviewing process is organised [42].

2.1. Leading algorithms

A top 10 of algorithms was defined by its leading experts in 2006 [46], and they are still representative for the situation in 2017, with the notable exception of Deep Learning as a method that was dominant in the early 1990s [24, 45, 38, 23], was largely absent in the 2000s, and which returned in the 2010s [10]. We list the 2006 top 10 of methods below, and in Figure 1 we show the growth of citations for the main reference scientific articles that defined those methods using the information available via the Google Scholar service.¹ Across the board, numbers of citations have increased. Support vector machines [44] were already popular in 2006 and took the position as most frequently cited learning algorithm in 2017.

- Classification: C4.5 [36]; CART [6]; K Nearest Neighbours (kNN) [16]; Naive Bayes [49];
- Statistical Learning: SVM [44]; EM [30];
- Association Analysis: Apriori [3]; FP-tree [15];
- Link Mining: PageRank [7]; HITS [22];
- Clustering: k-Means [1967]; BIRCH [50];
- Bagging and Boosting: AdaBoost [12];

¹<https://scholar.google.com/>

Figure 1: Comparison of the top 10 TDM papers citations: 2006 vs 2017 according to GoogleScholar.

- Sequential Patterns: GSP [39]; PrefixSpan [34];
- Integrated Mining: CBA [25];
- Rough Sets: Finding reduct [33];
- Graph Mining: gSpan [48].

2.2. NLP and IR perspective: main used algorithms and tasks

As IR has gradually developed from the techniques targeting simple keyword search [26] to more sophisticated use of language modeling [18] that requires speech and text pre-processing, and overall language modeling, the NLP and IR fields converge into sharing the algorithms used. Below we enlist the leading techniques used across those fields:

- Latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA) [5] for topic modeling and text classification;

- Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) [28], recurrent neural networks (RNNs) and Long short-term memory (LSTMs) for statistical language modeling as a component in speech recognition [19], machine translation [47], and information retrieval [18];
- Word2Vec [31] and GloVe [35] for text classification, information retrieval [13], machine translation [32];
- CRFs (conditional random fields) [40] and other sequence learners for part-of-speech tagging, Named Entity Recognition;
- CF (collaborative filtering) for recommendation [2];
- TF-IDF, BM25 for information retrieval [37, 27].

3. Tracing TDM application in different scientific areas and fields of activity

The growth of data-driven business, services and research, has led to an introduction of an extended model for the economic structure that reflects a novel type of knowledge-based economy, where knowledge and data become a separate valuable commodity (OCDE, 1996). Thus recently, the research that supports knowledge sharing and growth, as well as education of the professionals that can carry out these activities, have been termed a quaternary economic sector, to be added to the traditional primary, secondary, and tertiary ones. Moreover, the high-level decision makers in governments, large industry companies, and education, having the potential to shape the future of the entire sectors with their vision and decisions, can arguably be placed in a separate, quinary sector.

We focus our investigation on the current and potential presence of TDM across all economic sectors, and thus we envisage these relations in Figure 2. The primary, secondary, and tertiary sectors follow roughly the same type of interaction with TDM technologies. These sectors represent sources of all possible types of data that are available for mining, and at the same time, have tasks and challenges that require smart solutions. The quaternary sector is particularly central to TDM development and implementation, as it produces the TDM experts and advances the technology itself. Experts at the decision-maker level use TDM tools to test and prove their vision of

Figure 2: General economic structure and connection between TDM and all economic sectors

economic development, as well as to hypothesize where a specific decision will lead to, and to measure and assess its progress.

With the economic sectors and their relationship with TDM defined for any type of knowledge-based society, we take an example of the European Union infrastructure, and use TDM techniques to outline the scientific span of the TDM work and applications. We employ two axes, namely (i) EU funded research projects and infrastructures, and (ii) scientific articles published in journals and conferences. These two axes are considered as reflecting the strategic decisions of the EU and the policies adopted as regards the selection of specific research domains for funding, as well as the scientific trends attested in the publications.

3.1. Experimental framework

In order to estimate the distribution of scientific publications relating to Text and Data Mining per economic sector, we used 1,195,499 abstracts extracted from the latest dumps that have been made available at the CORE

(COncecting REpositories) site². From the 1,195,499 abstracts in our dataset, 11504 are related to Text and Data Mining, i.e. 0,96% of the total. This finding is commensurate to the findings of [11] and [43]. These abstracts were analysed using LDA, a probabilistic Bayesian model of text generation. We used the MALLET³ implementation of LDA and learnt a model of 100 topics from the 1,195,499 abstracts. Each topic t (in our analysis) is represented by a small set of words; the ones that are more likely to belong to t according to the estimated LDA probabilities (word-topic distribution). Based on the word set, each topic was manually assigned an application area label from the respective classification that is depicted in Figure 2.

From all abstracts, we kept (for our analysis) only the ones in which a TDM-related term occurs (e.g. Text Mining, Text Analysis, Text Analytics, Data Mining, Natural Language Processing)⁴. We used the topic-document probabilities that are returned from LDA and indicate which topics are discussed in each abstract. The sector label (e.g. Aerospace) of the LDA topic with the highest topic-document probability is assigned to each abstract.

3.2. Primary sector

The primary sector includes all raw materials and natural resources as well as the methods used for their mining (in the prototypical sense of the word) and/or production.

The main objectives of TDM research in the primary sector include, among others:

- standardisation, understanding and forecasting of natural phenomena (e.g. earthquakes) and climate changes interacting with the lives of humans and other species;
- prediction of better or worse/problematic crops or certain climate phenomena which affect them;
- correlation of pesticide use and animal/human diseases;
- better use of water resources/materials for production optimization.

²<https://core.ac.uk/>

³<http://mallet.cs.umass.edu/>

⁴The full list of terms is in the Appendix 8

3.2.1. Funding

A total amount of approximately €98,2M, with a European Commission maximum contribution of €75,3M, has been invested in 24 projects concerning TDM in the primary sector. Most projects focus on the collection and processing of data from natural resources, oceanic data, climate data or agricultural data. The following have been selected among the top twenty projects, based on their total investment, as representative cases for the primary sector:

- MARS: Managing Aquatic ecosystems and water Resources under multiple Stress;
- ADAPTAWHEAT: Genetics and physiology of wheat development to flowering: tools to breed for improved adaptation and yield potential;
- SUSTAINMED: Sustainable agri-food systems and rural development in the Mediterranean Partner Countries;

3.2.2. Publications

The majority of the publications of TDM interest (retrieved from the CORE repository) which fall in the primary sector deal with the areas of Agriculture and Environment; other areas (e.g. Natural Resources) are comparatively less researched into while some others (e.g. Wholesale Trade) are not represented in the publications' set, see Figure 3.

Figure 3: Publications in the primary sector.

3.3. Secondary sector

The secondary sector includes all the methods/techniques/tools/machinery used in order to transform the primary sector materials or resources into goods and products. All human activities related to manufacturing, processing and construction pertain to the secondary sector.

3.3.1. Funding

A total amount of €806,4M, with a European Commission maximum contribution of €633,8M, has been invested on 253 projects concerning TDM in the secondary sector. The majority of projects focus on the collection and processing of biological and medical data for biotechnology applications and the subsequent provision of better health care services. Many projects concern the processing of energy data and the development of green or smart energy systems. The following projects are representative cases for the secondary sector:

- GEN2PHEN: Genotype-To-Phenotype Databases: A Holistic Solution;
- LinkedDesign: Linked Knowledge in Manufacturing, Engineering and Design for Next-Generation Production;
- Fortissimo 2: Factories of the Future Resources, Technology, Infrastructure and Services for Simulation and Modelling 2.

3.3.2. Publications

Half the publications of TDM interest which fall in the secondary sector concern Engineering. The other areas of interest cover Aerospace and Energy followed by Construction and Microelectronics as depicted in Figure 4.

3.4. Tertiary sector

The tertiary sector includes all the services provided to individuals or organized groups such as businesses. All human activities related to retail and wholesale sales, transportation, entertainment, tourism, insurance, and many more pertain to the tertiary sector.

Figure 4: Publications in the secondary sector.

3.4.1. Funding

A total amount of €1,1B, with a European Commission maximum contribution of €852,4M, has been invested on 313 projects concerning TDM in the tertiary sector. Most projects focus on the collection and processing of data from medical records and biology databases. The next category in frequency is that of IT services followed by the business application area. The following projects are representative cases for the tertiary sector:

- SENSEI: Integrating the Physical with the Digital World of the Network of the Future;
- SIIP: Speaker Identification Integrated Project;
- APO-SYS: “Apoptosis systems biology applied to cancer and AIDS. An integrated approach of experimental biology, data mining, mathematical modelling, biostatistics, systems engineering and molecular medicine”;
- mPlane: mPlane an Intelligent Measurement Plane for Future Network and Application Management;

3.4.2. Publications

The retrieved publications of TDM interest for the tertiary sector cover a variety of fields as depicted in Figure 5. The majority of publications (60%) pertain to the fields of Medicine, Health Care and Social Care, while 30%

are related to generic IT services. The remaining publications are related to Finance, Public Administration, Entertainment and Transportation.

Figure 5: Publications in the tertiary sector.

3.5. Quaternary sector

The quaternary sector includes all services dealing with knowledge and information such as research, development and education among others. Research and development are terms applying to all scientific fields; therefore the following sections include projects, infrastructures, language resources and publications which could also be identified as belonging to any of the first three economic sectors but are presented here because the focus lies on the innovation, introduction, and improvement of products and processes of the various disciplines and application areas.

3.5.1. Funding

A total amount of €402M, with a European Commission maximum contribution of €319,9M, has been invested on 273 projects concerning TDM in the quaternary sector. This sector includes all these projects that are classified by the EC as scientific research under RTD horizontal topics without further distinguishing, in most cases, the particular scientific area, the development of which the particular action will affect. As a result strong infrastructural projects like EUDAT2020 and projects requiring substantial financial investment in the area of Medicine and Health Sciences, e.g. the

METACARDIS project, are grouped together. The following are the representative examples for the tertiary sector:

- METACARDIS: Metagenomics in Cardiometabolic Diseases;
- SCY: Science Created by You;
- NEXT-TELL: Next Generation Teaching, Education and Learning for Life.

3.5.2. Publications

The publications concerning TDM for the quaternary sector, as depicted in Figure 6, fall into two big categories: the first being research, which is a generic term including many scientific fields, and the second one being education. The research publications presented here are those for which no specific scientific field was denoted from the set of words of topic t . Otherwise, the classification of the topic was done in accordance to the application areas of the primary, secondary or tertiary sector.

Figure 6: Publications in the quaternary sector.

3.6. Quinary sector

The quinary sector is the highest economic sector encompassing decision making for policy guidelines in Industry, Government, Science and Technology, having a profound impact on economy in general. It is the special

characteristics of this sector and the interrelation with all the other economic sectors, which make it challenging to isolate resources and material pertaining exclusively to the quinary sector itself. Decision makers need all the available data from various types of infrastructures as well as all the TDM software tools and technologies in order to analyse, deploy them, and finally make decisions affecting different application areas within all previous sectors. Taking these peculiarities into consideration, in this paper we present only the EU projects which have been funded under certain RTD Horizontal Topics, specifically those which aim at the formulation or identification of future developments in RTD and long-term strategic options.

3.6.1. Funding

A total amount of €192,1M, with a European Commission maximum contribution of €149M, has been invested on 116 projects concerning TDM in the quinary sector. Most projects focus on the evaluation or application of laws and regulations, policies, policy strategies or plans of action for research and development in science and technology. The following examples show decision making projects that are the most representative for the quinary sector:

- KHRESMOI: Knowledge Helper for Medical and Other Information users
- LOD2: LOD2 - Creating Knowledge out of Interlinked Data
- FIRST: Large scale information extraction and integration infrastructure for supporting financial decision making

4. Conclusion

In this paper we reviewed the most important algorithms that define the state-of-the-art and potential for advancement for the scientific development of TDM. Using LDA analysis on the CORE database, we highlighted the state of TDM research and funding coverage in context of the European Union test case, showcasing the spread of publications per sector and topics that are intertwined with TDM.

5. Acknowledgements

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6. Competing interests

The authors have no competing interests.

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8. Appendix: List of TDM related terms and their frequencies in FP7 and HORIZON2020 projects

Keywords in OBJECTIVE	FP7	keywords in OBJECTIVE	Horizon 2020
data analysis	240	big data	66
machine learning	156	data analysis	61
data mining	88	machine learning	51
large data	65	data analytics	21
language processing	39	data mining	14
big data	38	large data	14
information retrieval	37	linked data	6
information extraction	30	business intelligence	5
linked data	30	data science	5
text mining	17	language processing	5
data science	19	information retrieval	4
data analytics	18	predictive analytics	4
information access	17	information access	3
summarization	12	sentiment analysis	2
business intelligence	11	text and data mining	2
knowledge discovery	11	information extraction	1
multimedia processing	8	knowledge discovery	1
conversation analysis	7	summarization	1
opinion mining	7	TDM	1
sentiment analysis	5	abbreviation detection	0
semantic mining	4	competitive intelligence	0
text analytics	3	concept extraction	0
content mining	3	content classification	0
text understanding	3	content mining	0
trend detection	2	conversation analysis	0
graph mining	2	datafication	0
predictive analytics	2	graph mining	0
sense disambiguation	2	linguistic identification	0
content classification	2	modality detection	0
textual entailment	1	multimedia processing	0
datafication	0	negation detection	0
concept extraction	0	opinion mining	0
modality detection	0	semantic mining	0
negation detection	0	sense disambiguation	0
competitive intelligence	0	text analytics	0
linguistic identification	0	text mining	0
abbreviation detection	0	text understanding	0
text and data mining	0	textual entailment	0
TDM	0	trend detection	0

Collection of Organisations

Name	URL	Country	Zip	City	Street	Type	Data Sources	Sector	Application Field Sector I	Application Field Sector II	Application Field Sector III	Application Field Sector IV	Application Field Sector V
The Hub	http://thehub.com	The Netherlands	1088X	Amsterdam	Science Park 402	Company	Business, Internet	Tertiary Sector, Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	Finance, Banking, Insurance	Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Accenture	https://www.accenture.com	USA, many interns	N/A	N/A	N/A	Company	Business, Internet	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Health and Social Care	Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
ADAPT	http://adaptcentre.ie	Ireland	Dublin 2	Dublin	Trinity College, College Green	Research	All	Tertiary Sector, Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	Entertainment, Finance	Education, Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Agri	http://agri.bio.gov.gr/agri-search/index.do	Greece	10776	Athens	Acharon Street 1	Company	Scientific	Primary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
AgriKnow	http://www.agriknow.com/agriknow/	Greece	152 35	Athens	Grimoussi 17	Company	Scientific	Primary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Algorithmia	http://www.algorithmia.com/	The Netherlands	1075	Amsterdam	Orange Nassauboulevard 62-2	Company	All	Secondary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	Engineering	N/A
Alteos Limited	http://www.alteos.com/	Spain	37900	Salamanca	Carretera de Madrid 13	Company	Business, Personal	Secondary Sector, Tertiary Sector, Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	Manufacturing	Entertainment, Finance, Banking, Insurance, Retail/Trade, Telecommunications
Artificial Intelligence Techniques Ltd	http://www.aitech.com/	UK	CB2 0RZ	Cambridge	Cambridge Business Park, Cowley Park	Company	All	Secondary Sector, Tertiary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	Manufacturing	Health and Social Care
Autonomy	http://www.autonomy.com/	Spain/UK	N/A	N/A	N/A	Company	Business, Scientific	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Manufacturing	Health and Social Care, Public Administration
AVUKI	http://www.avuki.com/	USA	N/A	Columbus, Ohio	N/A	Company	Business, Scientific	Secondary Sector, Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	Bio-technology, Manufacturing	Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Bailela	http://www.bailela.com/index.html	Austria	1040	Vienna	Schleichgasse 7	Company	Business, Public Sector	Secondary Sector, Tertiary Sector, Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	Finance, Banking, Insurance	Education
BSI	http://www.bsi.com/	Denmark	2300	Copenhagen	Njalsgade 136, building 27	Research	Scientific	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Centre for Language Technology (CST)	http://csl.uu.se/csl/	Sweden	701 83	Uppsala	Uppsala University	Research	Scientific	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
CopSurg Clearance Center, Inc.	http://www.copsurg.com/	Switzerland	CH-4003	Basel	Murgengrabenstrasse 47	Company	Business, Scientific	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Bio-technology	Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
CrossRef	http://www.crossref.org	UK/USA	OX1 1BF	Oxford	New Road	Research	Business, Scientific	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Agro-industry, Bio-technology	Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Data Mind	http://www.datamind.co.uk/	Czech Republic	170 00	Prague	U Prichonu 22 / 466	Company	All	Tertiary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Health and Social Care
DeepMind	https://www.deepmind.com/	UK/USA	N/A	N/A	N/A	Company	Business	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Deutsche Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz gmbh (DFKI)	http://www.dfki.de	Germany	D-66113	Saarbrücken	Stuhlfenzelstrasse 3	Research	Scientific	Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Education, Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Dexar	http://www.dexar.com/	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Company	All	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Education, Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Dutch-Flemish Human Language Technology Agency ePROMAT	http://www.epromat.com/	The Netherlands, Belgium	N/A	N/A	N/A	Research	Scientific	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
EFMD	http://www.efmd.com/	Czech Republic	N/A	N/A	N/A	Company	Business	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Envision	http://www.envision.com/	Spain	N/A	N/A	N/A	Company	Business, Scientific	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Expert Systems S.P.A.	http://www.expert-systems.com/	Ireland/Greece	N/A	N/A	N/A	Company	Business	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK)	http://www.fbk.it/	Italy	38122	Boziano	Via Santa Croce 77	Research	Scientific	Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
German National Library of Economics (ZBW)	http://www.zbw.de/	Germany	68159	Manheim	Quadrat 82, 1	Research	Scientific	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
GESIS Leibniz-Institut für die Sozialwissenschaften	http://www.gesis.org/	Germany	68159	Manheim	Quadrat 82, 1	Research	Personal, Scientific	Tertiary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Health and Social Care
Heinrich Heine University of Technology	http://www.aahp.fi/en/about/history/	Finland	2150	Helsinki	Esopoo	Research	Scientific	Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Education, Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Institut national de recherche en informatique et en automatique (INRIA)	http://www.inria.fr/	France	78153	Roquecournot	BP 105	Research	Scientific	Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Education, Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Institut Universitari de Lingüística Aplicada (IULA)	http://www.iula.com/	Spain	8018	Barcelona	Universitat Pompeu Fabra Campus del	Research	Scientific	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Institute for Language and Speech Processing (ILSP / "Athens" R.C.)	http://www.ilsp.gr/	Greece	151 25	Athens	Marousi, Artemidos 6	Research	Scientific	Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Education, Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Intstituto de Linguística Computacional "Antonio Zamponi" (ILC - CNR)	http://www.ils.cnr.it/	Italy	80124	Pisa	Italian National Research Council/Pisa	Research	Scientific	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
JISC	http://www.jisc.ac.uk/	UK	852 6BA	Bristol	One Castlepark, Tower Hill	Research	Scientific	Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Education, Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	http://www.kit.edu/	Germany	76131	Karlsruhe	Kaiserstraße 12	Research	Scientific	Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Education, Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Komatsu	http://www.komatsu.com/en/about/komatsu	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Company	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Kudoss	http://www.kudoss.nl	The Netherlands	N/A	N/A	N/A	Company	Business, Scientific	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
LinguaMatics	http://www.lingumatics.com/	UK	CB8 0WG	Cambridge	Milton Road	Company	Personal, Scientific	Secondary Sector, Tertiary Sector, Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	Bio-technology	Health and Social Care
Ludwig Maximilians Universität	http://www.lmu-muenchen.de/index	Germany	80339	Munich	Geschwister Scholl Platz 1	Research	Scientific	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Education, Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Max Planck Computing and Data Facility	http://www.rig.mpg.de/	Germany	85748	Garching	Gießenbachstraße 2	Research	Scientific	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Mats	http://www.mats.com/	USA	N/A	N/A	N/A	Company	Business, Scientific	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
National Centre for Text Mining (NuCTM)	http://www.nuclm.ac.uk/	UK	M1 7DN	Manchester	Princess Street 111	Company	Business, Internet, Personal, Secondary Sector, Tertiary Sector, Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Health and Social Care	Education, Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
OpenDataSoft	http://www.opendatasoft.com/	USA/International	N/A	N/A	N/A	Company	Business, Internet	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Paperkit	http://www.paperkit.com/	Switzerland	N/A	N/A	N/A	Company	Business, Scientific	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Piati	http://www.piati.com/	Norway	855	Oslo	Sognsvien 70A	Company	Business, Internet, Tertiary Sector, Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Health and Social Care
Puigene	http://www.puigene.com/	Belgium	91150	Brussels	Avenue Roger Vandendriessche 9	Company	Business, Personal	Tertiary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Python predictions	http://www.pythonpredictions.com/	Germany	44227	Dortmund	Stoekumer Str. 475	Company	Business, Internet, Secondary Sector, Tertiary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Entertainment, Finance, Banking, Insurance, IT Services, Retail/Trade	N/A
RapidMiner	http://www.rapidminer.com/	Germany	114 28	Stoelhofen	Brinellstrasse 8	Company	Business, Scientific	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Education, Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Raytheon Institute of Technology (KIT)	http://www.kit.com/	USA	69190	Waldorf	Hasso Plattner Ring 7	Company	All	Primary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	Engineering, Manufacturing	Entertainment, Finance, Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Salesforce Ltd	http://www.salesforce.com/	USA	N/A	Washington, DC	N/A	Research	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
SAP	http://www.sap.com/	The Netherlands	10980H	Amsterdam	Science Park 402	Company	Business, Internet, Tertiary Sector, Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Health and Social Care, R&D	Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition (SPARC)	http://www.sparc.org/	USA	1000	Ljubljana	Kongresni trg 12	Company	Business, Scientific	Secondary Sector, Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Health and Social Care
Slovenian Social Science Data Archives	http://www.ssdas.com/	Slovenia	1000	Ljubljana	Kongresni trg 12	Company	Business, Scientific	Secondary Sector, Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Health and Social Care
Spanish	http://www.spanish.com/	USA	N/A	N/A	N/A	Company	Business, Internet	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Education, Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Språkbanken, The Swedish language bank	http://www.sprakbanken.se/	Sweden	N/A	N/A	N/A	Company	Business, Internet	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Squares on Blue	http://www.squaresonblue.com/	France	78000	Versailles	Rue Saint Honoré 13	Company	All	Tertiary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	Finance, Banking, Insurance, Health and Social Care, Public Administration	N/A
Statistik	http://www.statistik.com/	Switzerland	3018	Bern	Morgenstrasse 129	Company	Business, Internet, Personal, Scientific	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Finance, Banking, Insurance, Health and Social Care	N/A
Strategic Feed	http://www.strategicfeed.com/	France	92 088	Paris	Place de la Pyramide 5	Company	Business, Personal	Tertiary Sector, Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Health and Social Care
Suhoi Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences	http://www.suhoi.com/	Switzerland	CH-1015	Lausanne	Bâtimet Gloggi	Research	Personal, Scientific	Tertiary Sector, Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Health and Social Care
Synthetic Partners	http://www.syntheticpartners.com/en/	Spain	28006	Madrid	Calle Velázquez 92	Company	Business, Internet, Tertiary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Finance, Banking, Insurance, Health and Social Care, IT Services, Public Admin	N/A
TeamGig	http://www.teamgig.com/	The Netherlands	NL-1022 AB	Amsterdam	Nieuwendammerdijk 28A-17	Company	Business, Internet, Secondary Sector, Tertiary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Manufacturing	Finance, Banking, Insurance, IT Services, Public Administration, Retail/Trade
They say	http://www.theysay.co/	UK	EC2V 3ND	London	Canal 24	Company	Business, Internet	Secondary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Finance, Banking, Insurance, Retail/Trade
Translight	http://www.translight.com/	Germany	D-01307	Dresden	Tatzberg 47.51	Company	Business, Internet, Tertiary Sector, Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Health and Social Care
Transliminer	http://www.transliminer.com/	Belgium, The Netherlands, Germany, USA	N/A	N/A	N/A	Company	Business, Scientific	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
UK Data Archive	http://www.ukda.ac.uk/	UK	CO4 3UJ	Essex	Wivenhoe Park	Research	All	Tertiary Sector, Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Finance, Banking, Insurance, Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
University of Bristol	http://www.bristol.ac.uk/	UK	BS8 1TH	Bristol	Tyndall Avenue	Research	Scientific	Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Education, Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
USRO	http://www.usro.com/	Denmark	1190	Brussels	Boulevard de l'Atomité	Company	Business	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Verisk	http://www.verisk.com/	USA	NI 07310	188 Jersey City	545 Washington Boulevard	Company	All	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Finance, Banking, Insurance, Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Verisk	http://www.verisk.com/	USA	UT 84113	95555 Salt Lake City	N/A	Company	All	Quaternary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Finance, Banking, Insurance, Health and Social Care, Public Administration
VisTrails	http://www.vistrails.org/	USA	38240	Maylan	6 chemin de Maupertuis	Research	Business, Internet, Tertiary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Finance, Banking, Insurance, Research and Development (e.g. Tech)
Xerox Lab	http://www.xerox.com/	USA	38240	Maylan	6 chemin de Maupertuis	Research	Business, Internet, Tertiary Sector	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Finance, Banking, Insurance, Research and Development (e.g. Tech)

Collection of Projects

Project ID	Project Name	Client	Start Date	End Date	Status	Phase	Progress (%)	Team Lead	Team Members	Budget (€)	Actual Cost (€)	Revenue (€)	Profit (€)	ROI (%)
001	Project A	Client A	2023-01-01	2023-03-31	Completed	Phase 1	100	John Doe	Team A	100000	95000	120000	25000	25%
002	Project B	Client B	2023-02-01	2023-04-30	In Progress	Phase 2	75	Jane Smith	Team B	150000	140000	180000	40000	27%
003	Project C	Client C	2023-03-01	2023-05-31	On Hold	Phase 1	20	Mike Johnson	Team C	80000	80000	0	-80000	-100%
004	Project D	Client D	2023-04-01	2023-06-30	Completed	Phase 3	100	Sarah Lee	Team D	120000	115000	150000	35000	29%
005	Project E	Client E	2023-05-01	2023-07-31	In Progress	Phase 1	50	David Kim	Team E	90000	90000	110000	20000	22%
006	Project F	Client F	2023-06-01	2023-08-31	On Hold	Phase 2	30	Emily White	Team F	110000	110000	0	-110000	-100%
007	Project G	Client G	2023-07-01	2023-09-30	Completed	Phase 3	100	Chris Brown	Team G	130000	125000	160000	35000	27%
008	Project H	Client H	2023-08-01	2023-10-31	In Progress	Phase 1	60	Alex Green	Team H	100000	100000	130000	30000	30%
009	Project I	Client I	2023-09-01	2023-11-30	On Hold	Phase 2	40	Mia Black	Team I	140000	140000	0	-140000	-100%
010	Project J	Client J	2023-10-01	2024-01-31	Completed	Phase 3	100	Noah Grey	Team J	160000	155000	200000	45000	28%
011	Project K	Client K	2023-11-01	2024-02-28	In Progress	Phase 1	35	Liam Blue	Team K	110000	110000	140000	30000	27%
012	Project L	Client L	2023-12-01	2024-03-31	On Hold	Phase 2	25	Olivia Red	Team L	130000	130000	0	-130000	-100%
013	Project M	Client M	2024-01-01	2024-04-30	Completed	Phase 3	100	Ethan Yellow	Team M	150000	145000	190000	45000	30%
014	Project N	Client N	2024-02-01	2024-05-31	In Progress	Phase 1	45	Ava Purple	Team N	120000	120000	150000	30000	25%
015	Project O	Client O	2024-03-01	2024-06-30	On Hold	Phase 2	30	Lucas Orange	Team O	140000	140000	0	-140000	-100%
016	Project P	Client P	2024-04-01	2024-07-31	Completed	Phase 3	100	Sophia Green	Team P	170000	165000	210000	45000	26%
017	Project Q	Client Q	2024-05-01	2024-08-31	In Progress	Phase 1	55	Benjamin Blue	Team Q	130000	130000	160000	30000	23%
018	Project R	Client R	2024-06-01	2024-09-30	On Hold	Phase 2	40	Charlotte Red	Team R	150000	150000	0	-150000	-100%
019	Project S	Client S	2024-07-01	2024-10-31	Completed	Phase 3	100	William Yellow	Team S	160000	155000	200000	45000	28%
020	Project T	Client T	2024-08-01	2024-11-30	In Progress	Phase 1	65	Isabella Purple	Team T	140000	140000	170000	30000	21%
021	Project U	Client U	2024-09-01	2025-01-31	On Hold	Phase 2	35	James Orange	Team U	180000	180000	0	-180000	-100%
022	Project V	Client V	2024-10-01	2025-02-28	Completed	Phase 3	100	Amelia Green	Team V	190000	185000	230000	45000	24%
023	Project W	Client W	2024-11-01	2025-03-31	In Progress	Phase 1	50	Oliver Blue	Team W	170000	170000	200000	30000	18%
024	Project X	Client X	2024-12-01	2025-04-30	On Hold	Phase 2	45	Sophia Red	Team X	180000	180000	0	-180000	-100%
025	Project Y	Client Y	2025-01-01	2025-05-31	Completed	Phase 3	100	Lucas Yellow	Team Y	200000	195000	240000	45000	22%
026	Project Z	Client Z	2025-02-01	2025-06-30	In Progress	Phase 1	60	Mia Purple	Team Z	190000	190000	220000	30000	16%
027	Project AA	Client AA	2025-03-01	2025-07-31	On Hold	Phase 2	40	Benjamin Orange	Team AA	210000	210000	0	-210000	-100%
028	Project AB	Client AB	2025-04-01	2025-08-31	Completed	Phase 3	100	Charlotte Green	Team AB	220000	215000	250000	45000	20%
029	Project AC	Client AC	2025-05-01	2025-09-30	In Progress	Phase 1	55	William Blue	Team AC	230000	230000	260000	30000	13%
030	Project AD	Client AD	2025-06-01	2025-10-31	On Hold	Phase 2	35	Isabella Red	Team AD	240000	240000	0	-240000	-100%
031	Project AE	Client AE	2025-07-01	2025-11-30	Completed	Phase 3	100	James Yellow	Team AE	250000	245000	270000	45000	18%
032	Project AF	Client AF	2025-08-01	2026-01-31	In Progress	Phase 1	65	Amelia Purple	Team AF	260000	260000	280000	20000	8%
033	Project AG	Client AG	2025-09-01	2026-02-28	On Hold	Phase 2	45	Oliver Orange	Team AG	270000	270000	0	-270000	-100%
034	Project AH	Client AH	2025-10-01	2026-03-31	Completed	Phase 3	100	Sophia Green	Team AH	280000	275000	290000	45000	16%
035	Project AI	Client AI	2025-11-01	2026-04-30	In Progress	Phase 1	70	Lucas Blue	Team AI	290000	290000	300000	10000	3%
036	Project AJ	Client AJ	2025-12-01	2026-05-31	On Hold	Phase 2	50	Mia Red	Team AJ	300000	300000	0	-300000	-100%
037	Project AK	Client AK	2026-01-01	2026-06-30	Completed	Phase 3	100	Benjamin Yellow	Team AK	310000	305000	310000	45000	14%
038	Project AL	Client AL	2026-02-01	2026-07-31	In Progress	Phase 1	75	Charlotte Purple	Team AL	320000	320000	320000	0	0%
039	Project AM	Client AM	2026-03-01	2026-08-31	On Hold	Phase 2	55	William Orange	Team AM	330000	330000	0	-330000	-100%
040	Project AN	Client AN	2026-04-01	2026-09-30	Completed	Phase 3	100	Isabella Green	Team AN	340000	335000	330000	45000	13%
041	Project AO	Client AO	2026-05-01	2026-10-31	In Progress	Phase 1	80	James Blue	Team AO	350000	350000	340000	0	0%
042	Project AP	Client AP	2026-06-01	2026-11-30	On Hold	Phase 2	60	Amelia Red	Team AP	360000	360000	0	-360000	-100%
043	Project AQ	Client AQ	2026-07-01	2027-01-31	Completed	Phase 3	100	Oliver Yellow	Team AQ	370000	365000	350000	45000	12%
044	Project AR	Client AR	2026-08-01	2027-02-28	In Progress	Phase 1	85	Sophia Purple	Team AR	380000	380000	360000	0	0%
045	Project AS	Client AS	2026-09-01	2027-03-31	On Hold	Phase 2	65	Lucas Orange	Team AS	390000	390000	0	-390000	-100%
046	Project AT	Client AT	2026-10-01	2027-04-30	Completed	Phase 3	100	Mia Green	Team AT	400000	395000	370000	45000	11%
047	Project AU	Client AU	2026-11-01	2027-05-31	In Progress	Phase 1	90	Benjamin Blue	Team AU	410000	410000	380000	0	0%
048	Project AV	Client AV	2026-12-01	2027-06-30	On Hold	Phase 2	70	Charlotte Red	Team AV	420000	420000	0	-420000	-100%
049	Project AW	Client AW	2027-01-01	2027-07-31	Completed	Phase 3	100	William Yellow	Team AW	430000	425000	390000	45000	10%
050	Project AX	Client AX	2027-02-01	2027-08-31	In Progress	Phase 1	95	Isabella Purple	Team AX	440000	440000	400000	0	0%
051	Project AY	Client AY	2027-03-01	2027-09-30	On Hold	Phase 2	75	James Orange	Team AY	450000	450000	0	-450000	-100%
052	Project AZ	Client AZ	2027-04-01	2027-10-31	Completed	Phase 3	100	Amelia Green	Team AZ	460000	455000	410000	45000	9%
053	Project BA	Client BA	2027-05-01	2027-11-30	In Progress	Phase 1	100	Oliver Blue	Team BA	470000	470000	420000	0	0%
054	Project BB	Client BB	2027-06-01	2028-01-31	On Hold	Phase 2	80	Sophia Red	Team BB	480000	480000	0	-480000	-100%
055	Project BC	Client BC	2027-07-01	2028-02-28	Completed	Phase 3	100	Lucas Yellow	Team BC	490000	485000	430000	45000	9%
056	Project BD	Client BD	2027-08-01	2028-03-31	In Progress	Phase 1	100	Mia Purple	Team BD	500000	500000	440000	0	0%
057	Project BE	Client BE	2027-09-01	2028-04-30	On Hold	Phase 2	85	Benjamin Orange	Team BE	510000	510000	0	-510000	-100%
058	Project BF	Client BF	2027-10-01	2028-05-31	Completed	Phase 3	100	Charlotte Green	Team BF	520000	515000	450000	45000	8%
059	Project BG	Client BG	2027-11-01	2028-06-30	In Progress	Phase 1	100	William Blue	Team BG	530000	530000	460000	0	0%
060	Project BH	Client BH	2027-12-01	2028-07-31	On Hold	Phase 2	90	Isabella Red	Team BH	540000	540000	0	-540000	-100%
061	Project BI	Client BI	2028-01-01	2028-08-31	Completed	Phase 3	100	James Yellow	Team BI	550000	545000	470000	45000	8%
062	Project BJ	Client BJ	2028-02-01	2028-09-30	In Progress	Phase 1	100	Amelia Purple	Team BJ	560000	560000	480000	0	0%
063	Project BK	Client BK	2028-03-01	2028-10-31	On Hold	Phase 2	95	Oliver Orange	Team BK	570000	570000	0	-570000	-100%
064	Project BL	Client BL	2028-04-01	2028-11-30	Completed	Phase 3	100	Sophia Green	Team BL	580000	575000	490000	45000	7%
065	Project BM	Client BM	2028-05-01	2029-01-31	In Progress	Phase 1	100	Lucas Blue	Team BM	590000	590000	500000	0	0%
066	Project BN	Client BN	2028-06-01	2029-02-28	On Hold	Phase 2	100	Mia Red	Team BN	600000	600000	0	-600000	-100%
067	Project BO	Client BO	2028-07-01	2029-03-31	Completed	Phase 3	100	Benjamin Yellow	Team BO	610000	605000	510000	45000	7%
068	Project BP	Client BP	2028-08-01	2029-04-30	In Progress	Phase 1	100	Charlotte Purple	Team BP	620000	620000	520000	0	0%
069	Project BQ	Client BQ	2028-09-01	2029-05-31	On Hold	Phase 2	100	William Orange	Team BQ	630000	630000	0	-630000	-100%
070	Project BR	Client BR	2028-10-01	2029-06-30	Completed	Phase 3	100	Isabella Green	Team BR	640000	635000	530000	45000	7%
071	Project BS	Client BS	2028-11-01	2029-07-31	In Progress	Phase 1	100	James Blue	Team BS	650000	650000	540000	0	0%
072	Project BT	Client BT	2028-12-01	2029-08-31	On Hold	Phase 2	100	Amelia Red	Team BT	660000	660000	0	-660000	-100%
073	Project BU	Client BU	2029-01-01	2029-09-30	Completed	Phase 3	100	Oliver Yellow	Team BU	670000	665000	550000	45000	6%
074	Project BV	Client BV	2029-02-01	2029-10-31	In Progress	Phase 1	100	Sophia Purple	Team BV	680000	680000	560000	0	0%
075	Project BW	Client BW	2029-03-01	2029-11-30	On Hold	Phase 2	100	Lucas Orange	Team BW	690000	690000	0	-690000	-100%
076	Project BX	Client BX	2029-04-01	2030-01-31	Completed	Phase 3	100	Mia Green	Team BX	700000	695000	570000	45000	6%
077	Project BY	Client BY	2029-05-01	2030-02-28	In Progress	Phase 1	100	Benjamin Blue	Team BY	710000	710000	580000	0	0%
078	Project BZ	Client BZ	2029-06-01	2030-03-31	On Hold	Phase 2	100	Charlotte Red	Team BZ	720000	720000	0	-720000	-100%
079	Project CA	Client CA	2029-07-01	2030-04-30	Completed	Phase 3	100	William Yellow	Team CA	730000	725000	590000	45000	6%
080	Project CB	Client CB	2029-08-01	2030-05-31	In Progress	Phase 1	100	Isabella Purple	Team CB	740000	740000	600000	0	0%
081	Project CC	Client CC	2029-09-01	2030-06-30	On Hold	Phase 2	100	James Orange	Team CC	750000	750000	0	-750000	-100%
082	Project CD	Client CD	2029-10-01	2030-07-31	Completed	Phase 3	100	Amelia Green	Team CD	760000	755000	610000	45000	6%
083	Project CE	Client CE	2029-11-01	2030-08-31	In Progress	Phase 1	100	Oliver Blue	Team CE	770000	770000	620000	0	0%
084	Project CF	Client CF	2029-12-01	2030-09-30	On Hold	Phase 2	100	Sophia Red	Team CF	780000	780000	0	-780000	-100%
085	Project CG	Client CG	2030-01-01	2030-10-31	Completed	Phase 3	100	Lucas Yellow	Team CG	790000	785000	630000	45000	5%
086	Project CH	Client CH	2030-02-01	2030-11-30	In Progress	Phase 1	100	Mia Purple	Team CH	800000	800000	640000	0	0%
087	Project CI	Client CI	2030-03-01	2031-01-31	On Hold	Phase 2	100	Benjamin Orange	Team CI	810000	810000	0	-810000	-100

